

UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI) Congress

Compute Allocation Breakout Session Report

22 October 2025, Leeds

This short report summarises the session on ‘Compute Allocation’ hosted by DSIT, UKRI, and EPCC at the UKRI DRI Congress 2025 in Leeds. The session began with a presentation by representatives from DSIT and UKRI on the UK compute landscape, followed by an open Q&A discussion.

Session led by:

- Felix Ruechardt, AI Compute Strategy, AIO, DSIT
- Richard Gunn, Digital Research Infrastructure Programme Director, UKRI
- Ritchie Somerville, Deputy Director, EPCC

Summary

The presentation covered key changes in the evolving landscape of compute in the UK, such as the UK Compute Roadmap, UKRI’s new mission (‘to advance knowledge, drive growth, and improve lives’), and how DRI aligns with the government priorities and missions. The presentation outlined the current AI compute allocation model, which provides rapid access to AI Research Resource (AIRR) and considers research and innovation projects for strategic AI functions and those aligned to national priorities. A simplified research workflow was presented, showing how data analysis, experimental data, AI, and modelling and simulation increasingly overlap. The discussion emphasised the importance of speed in allocation processes, noting that previous allocations on ARCHER2 could be completed in just two days.

Looking ahead, the presentation proposed a new model that balances community-driven activities with strategic priorities aligned to the UK Industrial Strategy. It also introduced the open science change model/pyramid, which aims to make research: possible (through research infrastructure), easy (by focusing on user experience), normative (through community engagement), rewarding (with incentives), and required (through compliance). Finally, it considered how allocation processes should accommodate a diverse range of users, from expert HPC practitioners to newcomers from emerging communities.

Q&A Discussion (categorised into common themes)

Communities

- **Q: Could you define communities?**
Communities refers to anyone supported by UKRI. It is important for service providers to support research communities beyond the direct infrastructure and allow those to contribute even if they are not part of a DRI host.
- **Q: How would you migrate multiple communities that are integrated differently into DRI?**
There shouldn't be barriers to accessing the platforms, but we need to consider the cost and resources involved when moving between platforms and learning new ways of working. There could be a way to break the vertical integration, where each layer is migrated sequentially as convergence is observed.
- **Q: Communities don't just self-aggregate; a structure is needed to actively form communities and it requires funding. How will you acknowledge existing communities and also create new communities noting not all users are part of a community?**
UKRI recognises it will continue to have a role in creating, developing and sustaining communities.
- **Comment: When communities are being defined, at the same time you are defining who is not in the community. You need to ensure people are not being excluded due to the definition.**
Noted. We will ensure that there are multiple routes for users to gain access and support.

Funding and allocation process

- **Q: What is the role of peer review in the allocation process?**
The level of detail has not yet been set. It would be difficult to remove peer review for accessing such a large investment, but whether it will take the same form as it does now is still to be determined and needs to proportionate. Peer review is important, but it could potentially be made more effective. For example, we could look at those who are considered 'fundable' and keep them on hold, allowing them to use some of the spare compute space when utilisation reaches 100%.
- **Q: How would you balance the national strategic priorities and scheduler priority?**
DSIT is still considering this. We don't want the system to be full all the time to the detriment of user experience, but we do want to backfill work that would still be of value (e.g., standby tickets).
- **Q: Do you want to make allocation units/credits consistent across DRI to allow credits to be portable, giving users flexibility and achieving greater efficiency? Also, to obtain market data?**

We will consider this. However, it could be difficult to implement effectively.

- **Q: On the prioritisation of finite compute resource using the rocks, pebbles and sand analogy, do you think there could potentially be too much focus on rocks, i.e., high-impactful research, and insufficient consideration of sand, which could still be valuable and impactful research?**

We would be developing a detailed allocation model that will balance varied impactful research at different scales and across the portfolio of compute services.

- **Q: The allocation process will shape the landscape. How will policy conflict and double jeopardy be addressed? How will you balance 'rock' (higher impact) and 'sand' (lower impact) projects, given that 'sand' projects could be key and pivotal for junior users in their early-stage projects?**

UKRI will be clear on what parameters are applied so users are aware of the expectations. There will be a quality control threshold in place. We recognise that creating a trusted solution will be key.

- **Q: When a project is co-funded or uses more than one infrastructure, how will it be managed in terms of assessment and peer review?**

This is a consideration, and a discussion will follow later.

- **Q: Will you ensure that you avoid double jeopardy in the allocation process with the rest of the funding process?**

Yes, noted.

- **Q: Are there going to be potentially anti-incumbencies bias towards new communities where the barrier is lowered for those new communities?**

We understand this risk and will consider this point in our plans.

- **Comment: On scalability, the way you allocate resources will affect project risk, as some projects are time-bound and cannot wait 3–6 months for allocation. The allocation system must support projects by ensuring that users know the likelihood of obtaining compute allocation so they can appropriately manage project risk.**

Noted.

- **Comment: In the future, if simulation systems are used to generate large amounts of data to form datasets for AI, then the allocation model will need to be changed.**

Noted.

Strategy

- **Q: How would you manage AI/simulation communities with new challenges?**

UKRI is open to hear what user support is needed and will be engaging further on this point. Some users may want to conduct both classical and AI simulations. From the

service provider's point of view, they would want to support researchers in doing both, e.g., Isambard has some experience supporting this.

- **Q: How would you support and leverage infrastructures, for example, to manage different system workflow requirements?**

The service provider will deliver against the agreed service level agreement with the funder while supporting user needs. The question that service providers are thinking is what latitude we want in the service.

- **Q: There could be challenges in new communities and in harmonising and linking data – would data stewardship and metadata support be of interest?**

There is significant opportunity in metadata by implementing automation. EPCC has been exploring this from a catalogue perspective and understanding which use cases drive impact. They are also considering whether data should be stored in one place. There is a push-pull balance to obtain community buy-in and identify incentives. As a service provider, ease of access is important in making the user experience smoother.

- **Q: Will data streaming (e.g., data from satellites or telescopes) fit into this model, or will it require more specialist resources?**

It will probably require more specialist support and resources. We need to think about how the data layer becomes a more coherent service that other components can feed into, where users who want to engage with the hardware as well as those who only want to access the top infrastructure level can do so as they wish.

- **Q: There's an OECD report that emphasises the importance of open science. How is an open science approach incorporated into your activities and strategy?**

UKRI supports open science and such approach is already embedded into current funding opportunities.

- **Comment: For international projects, more standardised technical stacks are needed and an understanding of international policies is important.**

Noted.

- **Q: Building DRI takes time, and timescales are quite long. How are you going to pivot to manage these timescales?**

There is a UK Compute Roadmap that describes the plan and DSIT is gaining knowledge on how to pivot, which will inform the scale up process.

- **Q: AI is going to be transformative and is valuable, but AI companies are over-valued. It's important to manage this risk. How are you preparing for this?**

This risk has been noted and is being considered.

- **Q: Are incentives just for users or for infrastructure providers? Are the incentives short, medium, or long term? How are you balancing all these incentives?**

Timescales and political factors may influence the incentives. It is important how we communicate the story of impact. The more we can amplify the impact, the better. This is important and something we can collectively do better on.